

Wumen Guan 無門關

also known as “The Gateless Barrier”, “The Gateless Gate”

By Guanxiong Qi, Florida State University

Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist text, Chan Buddhist text, Modern Buddhism, Text, Chinese Buddhism, Chinese Religion, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Japanese Religions, Japanese Buddhist Traditions, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Chan Buddhism (chan zong 禪宗), Korean Religions, Vietnamese Religions, Religious Group

Wumen Guan 無門關 (the Gateless Barrier) is a gong'an (公案; Jp. koan) collection by Wumen Huikai 無門慧開 (1183–1260), a Song dynasty Linji 臨濟 monk. Originally, for pedagogical purposes, Wumen Huikai selected 48 cases from two anterior gong'an compilations, Biyan lu 碧巖錄 (The Record of Blue Cliff) by Yuanwu Keqin 圓悟克勤 (1063–1135) and Congrong lu 從容錄 (The Record of Equanimity) by Hongzhi Zhengjue 宏智正覺 (1091–1157). Huikai commentated and gave a gāthā to each case. After Huikai's meditation instruction at the Longxiang Monastery in 1228, these 48 gong'an cases were compiled together and named the Wumen Guan. The title, Wumen Guan, is a pun that serves two meanings. “Wumen” is the name of the compiler, which literally means “no gate” or “gateless.” In this context, “no gate” implies “impossibility” or “no way.” “Guan,” a rhetorical term in Chinese religions, refers to the barrier of enlightenment as well as the breakthrough point toward awakening. Thus, from a literal perspective, the title refers to “the Barrier of Wumen” or the “Checkpoint of Wumen.” If we take “Wumen” as “gateless,” the collection is named “the Gateless Barrier,” “the Barrier that Has No Gate,” or “the Passage that Has No Way.” From an emic perspective, the Linji Chan tradition uses gong'an as expedient means to realize enlightenment. A gong'an is a short story, question, statement, or encounter dialogue of past Chan patriarchs, from the Sakyamuni Buddha to various Song lineage masters. These thematic stories are usually enigmatic and self-paradoxical. From a conventional perspective, many gong'an cases are absurd and non-sense. There are no standard answers to these gong'an cases, and giving official interpretations is regarded as taboo. Since the Song times, Chan Buddhists claimed Chan as a tradition of the secret mind-to-mind transmission that is devoid of verbal expression. The gong'an cases cannot be understood literally and straightforwardly, but need to be observed and comprehended by one's mind. Although this image of Chan tradition, according to modern scholars, is deviated from the historical facts, the tropes of mind-to-mind, master-to-disciple transmission are deeply embedded in the Song dynasty Chan texts, including the Wumen Guan. Accredited to Dahui Zonggao 大慧宗杲 (1089–1163), this method is referred to as Huatou Chan (話頭禪; Jp. Wato Zen). Facing the paradox, the practitioners need to raise and accumulate great doubt in the mind. As one pushes oneself to the brink of intellectual breakdown, one realizes great insights and enlightenment. Since its appearance, Wumen Guan received a great degree of popularity. However, there is no evidence that the text was massively promulgated and studied in China after Wumen Huikai's death, as its extent in Japan. After its transmission to Japan, the text became one of the quintessential texts of the Rinzai Zen tradition. There are dozens of extant editions with different degrees of variations. Many prescripts and postscripts are added continuously by famous Buddhist masters and scholar-officials. Some editions contain a 49th case added by Wu'an 無庵. In modern times, Wumen Guan is one of the most significant and popular Buddhist texts. It has been repetitively translated into multiple European languages.

Date Range: 1228 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Chan (Zen) Buddhism

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, Japan, Republic of Korea, Taiwan

The map covers the premodern regions and areas where *Wumen Guan* was read extensively. Because *Wumen Guan* is a distinctive Chan text, the map represents regions with strong withholding of Chan Buddhism, including China, Japan, Korea, and Vietnam. Since Chan Buddhism has become a "world religion" and *Wumen Guan* is internationally well-known, the map only indicates the presence of Chan Buddhism in premodern times.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yamada, Koun. *The Gateless Gate: The classic book of Zen koans*. Simon and Schuster, 2005.
- Source 2: *Two Zen classics: The Gateless Gate and the Blue Cliff Records*[M]. Shambhala Publications, 2005.
- Source 3: Gu, Guo. *Passing Through the Gateless Barrier: Koan Practice for Real Life*. Shambhala Publications, 2016.

Notes: Hsieh, Ding-hwa. "Poetry and Chan'Gong'an': From Xuedou Chongxian (980–1052) to *Wumen Huikai* (1183–1260)." *Journal of Song-Yuan Studies* 40.1 (2010): 39-70. Welter, Albert. "Zanning and Chan: The Changing Nature of Buddhism in Early Song China." *Journal of Chinese Religions* 23.1 (1995): 105-140. Poceski, Mario. "Killing Cats and Other Imaginary Happenings: Milieus and Features of Chan Exegesis." *Communities of Memory and Interpretation* (2018): 111. Welter, Albert. *The Linji lu and the creation of Chan orthodoxy: the development of Chan's records of sayings literature*. OUP USA, 2008.

Reference: Heine, Steven, and Dale S. Wright, eds.. *The Koan*. Edited by Steven Heine and Dale S. Wright. Oxford University Press on Demand, 2000. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Koan.html?hl=&id=Qs7wXsOte1AC.

Reference: Haskel, Peter. *Zen Master Tales*. Shambhala Publications, 2022. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eONIEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Heine, Steven, and Dale Wright. *Zen Masters*. Oxford University Press, 2010. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=cyYO-v4ICIsC>.

Reference: Welter, Albert. *Monks, Rulers, and Literati: The Political Ascendancy of Chan Buddhism*. USA: Oxford University Press, 2006. https://books.google.com/books/about/Monks_Rulers_and_Literati_The_Political.html?hl=&id=ODOIUv8NeWMC.

Reference: Yamada, Koun. *The Gateless Gate*. Simon and Schuster, 2005.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=VUA6AwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: MacHovec, Frank. Zen Classics. Lulu.com, 2009.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Zen_Classics.html?hl=&id=6huFAGAAQBAJ.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://terebess.hu/zen/mumonkan-eng.html>
- Source 1 Description: Information about Wumen Guan collected by the Terebess Center.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/bud/zen/mumonkan.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Translation of Wumen Guan by the late Zen master Katsuki Sekida
- Source 3 URL: <http://fo.sina.com.cn/intro/lecture/2017-08-15/doc-ifyixias1089743.shtml>
- Source 3 Description: Transcript of Wumen Guan sermon by Master Jinghui.
- Source 1 URL: <https://tricycle.org/magazine/the-best-season/>
- Source 1 Description: Tricycle article about Wumen Huikai
- Source 2 URL: <https://tallahasseechan.org/teachings/publications/passing-through-the-gateless-barrier/>
- Source 2 Description: Information about one Wumen Guan translation

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra19/T48n2005.pdf
- Source 1 Description: The Cbeta version of Wumen Guan
- Source 2 URL: <https://zh.m.wikisource.org/zh-hant/%E7%84%A1%E9%96%80%E9%97%9C>
- Source 2 Description: The Wiki text version of Wumen Guan
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.bdkamerica.org/product/three-chan-classics/>
- Source 3 Description: Wumen Guan translated by BDK

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: The text is not required to store at a specific location. Each monastery has a Sutra Hall for scripture storage. However, Wumen Guan is a widely circulated text. Both monastics and laities can hold it. In modern times, it has become a classical Chan reader. In general, no specific location is prescribed for storage.

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Wumen Guan was first a selection of gong'an used for the monastic summer meditation retreat. After, it was recorded by Zongshao 宗紹, a disciple of Wumen Huikai and a participant of the retreat. As a compilation, the text is built upon previous gong'an collections. Then, the text is edited and finalized as a written text in ancient Chinese style.

↳ Inked

—with Ink

Notes: Wumen Guan was composed as a written text. Presumably, as always in a medieval Chinese context, it was written with a brush on paper. Then, it was copied and printed on paper.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

— Paper

Notes: In the Song times, hemp paper was widely used in everyday life, from governmental paperwork to printed paper notes. Since Wumen Guan was composed in the 13th century China, it is very likely that it was first written on pieces of hemp paper. In later times, while hand-copying remains a popular practice in East Asia, the book is massively printed on regular paper.

↳ Specify type of paper

—Specify: Hemp Paper

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

— No

Notes: Typically, the text is not stored with any iconography or image. There is no general rule regarding it. Chan is a tradition that self-claims to be detached from verbal expressions and images. However, for Chan/Zen practitioners, beside the scripture, it is common to find the "Wu" symbol, a portrait of Bodhidharma, or paintings about other Chan lineage masters.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

—Other [specify]: No, the text material is not modified before writing. The disciple needs to quickly jot down the master's teaching, so the writing process likely didn't involve any ritual.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

— No

Notes: In most cases, the text is not stored with any an-iconic image. Most of the Chan images are clear signifiers to the tradition.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

—Other [specify]: For the most of the cases, the text remains the same. Sometimes, the text is modified into different renditions, with new prefaces or postscripts added.

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

— No

Notes: Chan, regarded by many scholars, is a spontaneous Chinese movement. Despite many lineage masters allegedly having royal connections or serving the preceptor of the nation, the production of Chinese Buddhist scriptures usually relies on lay donations, instead of funding from any polity. Buddhism was never the "state religion" of China, and therefore, no polity has the willing to facilitate the Chan scriptures production. In Japan, the situation is more complex. During the Kamakura period--when each Buddhist sect was backed up by the local warlord--the production of Wumen Guan might be supported by the local polity. However, the possibility is considerably rare.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

— Total audience: 500000000

Notes: I will tentatively count the number of self-identified Buddhist according to various databases. The worlddata.info, see <https://www.worlddata.info/religions/buddhism.php>, suggests there are 400 million Buddhists. According to the Pew Research Center, there are about 500 million Buddhists worldwide, see <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-exec>. From a general perspective, all Buddhists are the intended audience. Of course, Wumen Guan is popular and available for everyone to read.

Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

— Number: 350000000

Notes: According to the Pew Research Center, more than 98% percent of Buddhists are Asian. Since Chan Buddhism is an East Asian tradition, I counted the number of Buddhists in China, Korea, Japan, and Vietnam. Based on the data, there are about 350,000,000 Buddhists in East Asian countries.

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

—smallest audience: 2000000

Notes: North Korea reportedly has the smallest Buddhist population, around 2 million people. Different sources give different answers. For some reference, see <https://www.state.gov/reports/2020-report-on-international-religious-freedom/north-korea/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Religion_in_North_Korea

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

—largest audience: 270000000

Notes: China has the largest number of Buddhists, range from 250 million to 300 million. For some reference, see <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-buddhist/>; <https://www.cfr.org/backgroundunder/religion-china>

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

—Specify: In the East Asian countries, there were multiplied incidents of anti-Buddhist movement. For example, the Communist anti-religion police prohibited religious practices in its ruled area.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

—Number: 20

Notes: Roughly 20% percent of the East Asian population are self-identified Buddhists. <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-buddhist/>

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

—smallest audience: 10

Notes: Again, multiple sources provide different data. It is estimated that 10% of North Korean are Buddhists.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

—largest audience: 36

Notes: Japan has statistically the largest number of Buddhists, about 35-67 percent, based on different criteria. <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/buddhist-countries>; <https://www.japan-guide.com/e/e2055.html>

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

—Specify: In the East Asian countries, there were multiplied incidents of anti-Buddhist movement. For example, the Communist anti-religion police prohibited religious practices in its ruled area.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

- Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)
- Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Notes: Chan/Zen Buddhism is considered as a school of Mahayana Buddhism. At the same time, the Chan/Zen tradition is a large tradition with many different sub-sects. The intended audiences of the scriptures are mostly Buddhists. Despite Buddhists trying to enforce conversion, in Asia, only a marginal number of people convert to Buddhism. The Buddhists, especially Mahayana Buddhists are the intended audience.

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

- No

Notes: *Wumen Guan* and other similar Chan texts have very vague statuses. On the one hand, they are "religious" scripture, loaded with religious jargon and denotations. On the other hand, they are open to interpretation. In this sense, the notion of the audience, whether from an emic or an etic perspective, is the same. Any Buddhist or anyone who is interested in Buddhism is part of its readership, including scholars.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

- Yes

Notes: Buddhist monastics are the professional who promote the religion and scriptures.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

- No

Notes: The text itself does not contain any information about proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

- No

Notes: The text itself does not contain any information about proselytization.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

- No

Notes: No reward is promised in the text per se. However, from a general Buddhist perspective, the promulgation of scripture is encouraged but not forced. Specifically about the Chan tradition, the proselytization of scripture is not encouraged, since it is labeled as the tradition beyond words and letters.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

- No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any related content.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not specifically mention proselytization per se.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: In a way, Chan Buddhism culturally proselytizes itself without being explicit about it. It had become a part of popular culture worldwide. Despite the text is silent on the subject, these popular cultures draw people to Buddhism.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is silent on this matter.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Wumen Guan is institutionally considered a canonical text. Formal monastics use it to train disciples and it is widely read by the laity. It is contained in numerous canon, for example, see http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T48n2005_001.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

Notes: Different from various Buddhist sutras (the speech/preach of the Buddha), Wumen Guan and many Chan literature are composed by regular Chinese monastics. They, despite being viewed as canonical, are not recited in the assembly nor privately. There is no culture of oral recitation for the Chan gong'an case.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Chan/Zen Buddhism is often described as a-theist and non-ritualist. Though this portrayal is inaccurate in many ways, looking at its scriptural basis, divine beings plays a much lesser and minor role, in comparison with other Buddhist texts. Wumen Guan has a clear origin. It is a man-made compilation of the gong'an cases taught by Wumen. More information is in the description.

Reference: Gregory, Peter, and Daniel Getz, eds.. BUDDHISM IN THE SUNG. Edited by Peter Gregory and Daniel Getz. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2022.

↳ Revealed by a high god?

— No

Notes: The text rarely mentions divine beings, such as Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and devas.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

— No

Notes: The text rarely mentions divine beings, such as Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and devas.

↳ Inspired by high god?

— No

Notes: The question is difficult to answer. From an orthodox perspective, all Buddhist-related materials are "inspired" by the Buddha, since the Buddha gave rise to Buddhism. However, specifically, the compilation of *Wumen Guan* has little to do with the inspiration from the Buddha.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

— No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

— No

Notes: The question is whether we shall count enlightened humans as "divine" or not. In my opinion, the Buddhist sense of enlightenment is different from the idea of the "divine." The masters are enlightened but do not possess any divine power.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

— Yes

Notes: Yes, after Huikai's meditation instruction at the Longxiang Monastery in 1228, these 48 gong'an cases were compiled together and named the *Wumen Guan*.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

— Yes

Notes: Considering the extant more than a dozen editions of *Wumen Guan*, the text is alterable. Many editions have added prefaces or postscript, and some added a new case. One can also make commentaries on the cases and make them into new books. For more info, see <https://terebeess.hu/zen/mumonkan-eng.html>. Also, the *Wumen Guan* shares many same stories with other gong'an compilations. Therefore, practitioners can choose to use other collections to practice as substitutes.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

— Yes

Notes: Since it is not a sutra, practitioners are more open-minded toward the alteration of the content. The words are only the means and tools for religious cultivation. If the scripture is working, as a meditation guide, practitioners have no problems to accept it.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

— Yes

Notes: Chan/Zen Buddhism, currently, is a very distinct institution of Buddhism with a clear identity. In medieval China, there are doubts about the degree of its institutionalization. Nonetheless, there is no doubt that Chan/Zen Buddhism had and has its religious community and identity.

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. *How Zen Became Zen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

Reference: Jia, Jinhua. *The Hongzhou School of Chan Buddhism in Eighth- Through Tenth-century China*. State University of New York Press, 2012.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2gvurBf_sqAC.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

— Yes

Notes: Normally, Buddhist monastics have the rightful skills and authority to interpret the scriptures. Usually, lay people can also make interpretations and scholastic debates about seminal Buddhist scriptures. These lay interpretations can easily spread in the lay practitioners' social circle. For example, the famous Buddhist scholar, Nan Huajin, commented numerous Chan gong'an, see <https://www.jianshu.com/p/1e6f0b37edf4>.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

— No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

— No

Notes: There are no common disagreements. In fact, a gong'an does not have a clear, definitive answer. Thus, it is very common that people have totally different understandings. However, no common disagreements exist between different "schools."

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

— No

Notes: Since there is little major disagreement, there is little resolving debate.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Everyone is welcomed to transmit the scripture, but the Chan monastics are the professionals. The Buddhist monastics are specially trained clerics who dedicate their whole life to the spread and perfection of Buddhism.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: No. Although most of the renowned monastics are males, East Asian Buddhism has both Bhikkhu Sangha and Bhikkhuni Sangha, which encompass the female and male genders. There is no gender exclusion rule.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

Notes: There is no age limit.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Notes: Buddhism, as a social institution, historically encourages translations and localizations. People can teach, preach, write, and copy the sutra in the language they wish. *Wumen Guan*, as well, is translated and taught in many different languages.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: For example, *Wumen Guan* is cataloged as the T.48, No.2005 in the Taisho canon.

Reference: Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. *Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing*. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Storch, Tanya. *The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka*. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Wu, Jiang, and Greg Wilkinson. *Reinventing the Tripitaka*. Lexington Books, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=m084DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism has its very specific meaning of Tripitaka. And the Amitabha sutra is contained in both Mahayana canons--the Tibetan and Chinese canons. Neither canon is permanently closed. The contained scriptures and the catalogs are changing constantly. The canonicity of some sutras are viewed differently sometimes.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

— No

Notes: Wumen Guan, specifically, does not have any official or publically accepted commentaries, nor any commentary is included in the Buddhist canons. Again, giving official interpretation is forbidden in Chan Buddhism.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

— No

Notes: In the Song times, Wumen Guan was composed in China with little/no foreign cultural influence (except the whole religion of Buddhism). It was written in Chinese, which was not considered as a sacred language.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

— No

Notes: The Chan/Zen tradition is, considerably, sticks to its own doctrines and teachings. It is partially because of the imagined/constructed idea of the transmission of the lineage (and the lineage master). Also, it is because Chan is a tradition focused on practice and experience.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

— No

Notes: The text itself does not relate to any ritual practice. The Chan/Zen tradition is often described as a non-ritualist religion (despite there being a lot in reality, such as respecting the master and bowing to the three Jewels). If we consider meditation as a ritual, we may say "yes" to the question. However, most of the people would not count meditation as a type of ritual.

Is there material significance to the text?

— No

Notes: Again, the Chan/Zen tradition claims itself as a tradition of mind-to-mind transmission. It requires the practitioners to not cling on any material matter. Despite there are numerous items involved in the daily practice of Buddhism, Wumen Guan, and other related Chan texts, does not have any significant material related to them.

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

— No

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– No

Notes: The question is difficult to answer. From an orthodox perspective, all Buddhist-related materials are "inspired" by the Buddha, since the Buddha gave rise to Buddhism. However, specifically, the compilation of Wumen Guan has little to do with the inspiration from the Buddha.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

Notes: The question is whether we shall count enlightened humans as "divine" or not. In my opinion, the Buddhist sense of enlightenment is different from the idea of the "divine." The masters are enlightened but do not possess any divine power.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, after Huikai's meditation instruction at the Longxiang Monastery in 1228, these 48 gong'an cases were compiled together and named the Wumen Guan.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: Considering the extant more than a dozen editions of Wumen Guan, the text is alterable. Many editions have added prefaces or postscript, and some added a new case. One can also make commentaries on the cases and make them into new books. For more info, see <https://terebess.hu/zen/mumonkan-eng.html>. Also, the Wumen Guan shares many same stories with other gong'an compilations. Therefore, practitioners can choose to use other collections to practice as substitutes.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: Since it is not a sutra, practitioners are more open-minded toward the alteration of the content. The words are only the means and tools for religious cultivation. If the scripture is working, as a meditation guide, practitioners have no problems to accept it.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Chan/Zen Buddhism, currently, is a very distinct institution of Buddhism with a clear identity. In medieval China, there are doubts about the degree of its institutionalization. Nonetheless, there is no doubt that Chan/Zen Buddhism had and has its religious community and identity.

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. *How Zen Became Zen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

Reference: Jia, Jinhua. *The Hongzhou School of Chan Buddhism in Eighth- Through Tenth-century China*. State University of New York Press, 2012.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2gvurBf_sqAC.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: Normally, Buddhist monastics have the rightful skills and authority to interpret the scriptures. Usually, lay people can also make interpretations and scholastic debates about seminal Buddhist scriptures. These lay interpretations can easily spread in the lay practitioners' social circle. For example, the famous Buddhist scholar, Nan Huajin, commented numerous Chan gong'an, see <https://www.jianshu.com/p/1e6f0b37edf4>.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

Notes: There are no common disagreements. In fact, a gong'an does not have a clear, definitive answer. Thus, it is very common that people have totally different understandings. However, no common disagreements exist between different "schools."

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

Notes: Since there is little major disagreement, there is little resolving debate.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Everyone is welcomed to transmit the scripture, but the Chan monastic are the professionals. The Buddhist monastics are specially trained clerics who dedicate their whole life to the spread and perfection of Buddhism.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: No. Although most of the renowned monastics are males, East Asian Buddhism has both Bhikkhu Sangha and Bhikkhuni Sangha, which encompass the female and male genders. There is no gender exclusion rule.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

Notes: There is no age limit.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Notes: Buddhism, as a social institution, historically encourages translations and localizations. People can teach, preach, write, and copy the sutra in the language they wish. Wumen Guan, as well, is translated and taught in many different languages.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: For example, Wumen Guan is cataloged as the T.48, No.2005 in the Taisho canon.

Reference: Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Storch, Tanya. The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Wu, Jiang, and Greg Wilkinson. Reinventing the Tripitaka. Lexington Books, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=m084DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism has its very specific meaning of Tripitaka. And the Amitabha sutra is contained in both Mahayana canons--the Tibetan and Chinese canons. Neither canon is permanently closed. The contained scriptures and the catalogs are changing constantly. The canonicity of some sutras are viewed differently sometimes.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Notes: Wumen Guan, specifically, does not have any official or publically accepted commentaries, nor any commentary is included in the Buddhist canons. Again, giving official interpretation is forbidden in Chan Buddhism.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: In the Song times, Wumen Guan was composed in China with little/no foreign cultural influence (except the whole religion of Buddhism). It was written in Chinese, which was not considered as a sacred language.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 500000000

Notes: I will tentatively count the number of self-identified Buddhist according to various databases. The worlddata.info, see <https://www.worlddata.info/religions/buddhism.php>, suggests there are 400

million Buddhists. According to the Pew Research Center, there are about 500 million Buddhists worldwide, see <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-exec>. From a general perspective, all Buddhists are the intended audience. Of course, Women Guan is popular and available for everyone to read.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 350000000

Notes: According to the Pew Research Center, more than 98% percent of Buddhists are Asian. Since Chan Buddhism is an East Asian tradition, I counted the number of Buddhists in China, Korea, Japan, and Vietnam. Based on the data, there are about 350,000,000 Buddhists in East Asian countries.

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

Notes: North Korea reportedly has the smallest Buddhist population, around 2 million people. Different sources give different answers. For some reference, see <https://www.state.gov/reports/2020-report-on-international-religious-freedom/north-korea/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Religion_in_North_Korea

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 270000000

Notes: China has the largest number of Buddhists, range from 250 million to 300 million. For some reference, see <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-buddhist/>; <https://www.cfr.org/background/religion-china>

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: In the East Asian countries, there were multiplied incidents of anti-Buddhist movement. For example, the Communist anti-religion police prohibited religious practices in its ruled area.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 20

Notes: Roughly 20% percent of the East Asian population are self-identified Buddhists. <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2012/12/18/global-religious-landscape-buddhist/>

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10

Notes: Again, multiple sources provide different data. It is estimated that 10% of North Korean are Buddhists.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 36

Notes: Japan has statistically the largest number of Buddhists, about 35-67 percent, based on different criteria. <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/buddhist-countries>; <https://www.japan-guide.com/e/e2055.html>

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: In the East Asian countries, there were multiplied incidents of anti-Buddhist movement. For example, the Communist anti-religion police prohibited religious practices in its ruled area.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Notes: Chan/Zen Buddhism is considered as a school of Mahayana Buddhism. At the same time, the Chan/Zen tradition is a large tradition with many different sub-sects. The intended audiences of the scriptures are mostly Buddhists. Despite Buddhists trying to enforce conversion, in Asia, only a marginal number of people convert to Buddhism. The Buddhists, especially Mahayana Buddhists are the intended audience.

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: *Wumen Guan* and other similar Chan texts have very vague statuses. On the one hand, they are "religious" scripture, loaded with religious jargon and denotations. On the other hand, they are open to interpretation. In this sense, the notion of the audience, whether from an emic or an etic perspective, is the same. Any Buddhist or anyone who is interested in Buddhism is part of its readership, including scholars.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist monastics are the professional who promote the religion and scriptures.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not contain any information about proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not contain any information about proselytization.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: No reward is promised in the text per se. However, from a general Buddhist perspective, the promulgation of scripture is encouraged but not forced. Specifically about the Chan tradition, the proselytization of scripture is not encouraged, since it is labeled as the tradition beyond words and letters.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any related content.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not specifically mention proselytization per se.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: In a way, Chan Buddhism culturally proselytizes itself without being explicit about it. It had become a part of popular culture worldwide. Despite the text is silent on the subject, these popular cultures draw people to Buddhism.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is silent on this matter.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: The Chan/Zen tradition is, considerably, sticks to its own doctrines and teachings. It is partially because of the imagined/constructed idea of the transmission of the lineage (and the lineage master). Also, it is because Chan is a tradition focused on practice and experience.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not relate to any ritual practice. The Chan/Zen tradition is often described as

a non-ritualist religion (despite there being a lot in reality, such as respecting the master and bowing to the three Jewels). If we consider meditation as a ritual, we may say "yes" to the question. However, most of the people would not count meditation as a type of ritual.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: Again, the Chan/Zen tradition claims itself as a tradition of mind-to-mind transmission. It requires the practitioners to not cling on any material matter. Despite there are numerous items involved in the daily practice of Buddhism, Wumen Guan, and other related Chan texts, does not have any significant material related to them.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not a topic in the text. On the contrary, Buddhism generally advocate the inseparability of spirit and the body (and deny the existence of a self).

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not explicitly have any content relate to supernatural monitoring.

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Menu

Notes: Wumen Guan is comprised of 48 gong'an cases. Before the main content, a menu, consisting of the titles of the 48 stories, is given. See http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T48n2005_001

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Upholding full sexual abstinence is presumed for Buddhist monastics. However, the text does not contain any code related to the subject.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The text provides no social norms. They are the gong'an cases for religious practices.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The Chan tradition is often characterized as a tradition of self-power, which means one can only rely on one's own effort to reach enlightenment. Though this image is constructed mainly by Japanese

sectarians and projected back to Chinese Buddhist history, many Chan classics lack messianic figures. There is no belief that, the worship of a certain figure can lead the believers to salvation.

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The text is sometimes accompanied by calligraphy or a painting inspired by a gong'an case.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: Copy of *Wumen Guan* is often accompanied by the calligraphy of some of its key phrases or one central idea.

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: There are portrayals of the lineage masters and the paintings regarding the specific gong'an case.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Although Chan Buddhism is famous for its construction of the notions of lineage master and lineage chart, *Wumen Guan* does not contain such a genealogy chart. The gong'an stories mention the names of many famous lineage masters, such as Zhaozhou Congnian and Baizhang Huaihan. However, the relationship between these masters is not explicated in the text. Also, the text does not name any Buddhist lineage.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not give any systematic explanation of the afterlife. Though Buddhism typically stick to the idea of samsara (the six realms of rebirth), the text itself is not related to such discussion. At the same time, Chan/Zen Buddhism sometimes philosophically deny the existence of samsara.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify any rules about sexuality. It is presumed that all Buddhists need to obey the precepts, which include the constraint of sexual activities. However, *Wumen Guan* lack such content.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text does not make any moral requirement or distinction. No issue regarding morality or legality is discussed.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Albeit Buddhism generally has a few eschatologist theories, none of those appear in *Wumen Guan*. The Chan tradition is less associated with the idea of the beginning of a new epoch. It is also because Chan Buddhism lacks a messianic figure.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Some actions/results in the text can be seen as punishment. For example, in the case of Wild Fox Chan, the monastic was reborn into a fox because he failed to comprehend the nature of causation (*hetu-phala*). However, even we call it a punishment, such result is not meted out by any supernatural being.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are more than a dozen editions of *Wumen Guan*. Many editions have added prefaces or postscript, and some added a new case. One can also make commentaries on the cases and make them into new books. In general, the core contents remain the same. In modern days, the text is translated into multiple languages, and there are at least a dozen versions available in English. For more info, see <https://terebess.hu/zen/mumonkan-eng.html>.

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There is no core difference between different editions. The core content remains more or less the same.

If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Chan/Zen masters, after realizing their unique understanding of the gong'an cases, often add a new preface or postscript. The differentiation comes with these prefaces and postscript. They were added by different people and at different times. Some even add additional gong'an cases to the compilation.

Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Practitioners will follow the version that is convenient to them. Again, the contents of all the editions are almost the same. The preface and postscript do not really matter at the most of the time.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text contain no information about castration.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Legal code is the subject matter of the Vinaya text. Chan gong'an collection is not related to the monastic rules.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The idea of reincarnation is employed in some cases of Wumen Guan. However, these stories are more rhetorical than doctrinal. The text does not specify any systematic idea of reincarnation.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Wumen Guan is generally included in the post-Song Chinese Buddhist Canon as a Chan text.

Reference: Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Storch, Tanya. The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Lopez, Donald S.. Buddhist Scriptures. Penguin UK, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=6Pd-2IIZip4C>.

Reference: Lock, Graham, and Gary S. Linebarger. Chinese Buddhist Texts. Routledge, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=btJMDwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

— Yes

Notes: The text is commonly included in the post-Song Chinese Buddhist canon. As a Chan text, it cannot be found in the Pali and Tibetan canons.

↳ How is the authority established?

— Yes

Notes: The authority of the text is based on the authority of its author. Since Wumen Huikai was publically recognized as a renowned (and likely enlightened) Chan master, he has the authority and the influence to spread the text. As more people read the text and admit its value, the text was gradually canonized.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

— Yes

Notes: Yes, Buddhist canons are usually open canon. It means people can alter and add the canon according to the context.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

— No

Notes: Since its initial inclusion into the canon, its canonicity was rarely questioned. Since then, Wumen Guan is a popular and authoritative Chan text.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

— No

Notes: Wumen Guan is a stand-alone text. It means it was not composed as a part of a series nor designed for a larger textual corpse.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

— No

Notes: Enlightened individuals can only teach certain things, but cannot straightforwardly bestow rewards. It depends on one's self to seek benefits from the teaching of the enlightened.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

— No

Notes: Again, the text does not discuss any moral issues. And "virtue" is often not the best term used for the Buddhist tradition. One's salvation is gained from one's own practice and wisdom, but not the possession of virtues.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The text does not mention fasting.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not give any related instruction.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The text is very explicitly a scripture. Although it was not deemed as canonical as many of the sutras--since it was the instruction of a Chan master but not the Buddha--the text clearly has a religious orientation and is used for religious cultivation.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: No religious calendar nor any dating is provided in the text.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text does not talk about burial nor sacrifices.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Chinese/East Asian Buddhism has rigid precepts regarding the intake of food. However, Wumen Guan does not contain any information. Such topics are discussed in Vinaya text instead.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text mentions similar topics, such as the master cutting off the finger of the disciple in the story of One Finger Chan. However, it is not a requirement.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: No related idea is discussed in the text.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: No burial instruction or system is described in the text.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain related information.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not presented in the text.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the definition of "supernatural beings." In some cases, spiritual beings, such as shapeshifters and ghosts, exist. For example, in case 2 (Wild Fox Chan), there is a shapeshifter fox (ex-Buddhist trapped in the fox shape; 於過去迦葉佛時。曾住此山。因學人問。大修行底人還落因果。也無。某甲對云。不落因果。五百生墮野狐身。今請和尚。). In some stories, enlightened Buddhist individuals, such as bodhisattvas, exist, such as the case of "Lady in Samadhi" (世尊昔因文殊至諸佛集處。值諸佛各還本處。)

A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: The notion of a supreme high-god (as in the Judeo-Christian tradition) is lacking in Chan/Zen Buddhism. The answer to the question is determined by the definition of "Supreme High God." The Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and Chan lineage masters are not the creators of the universe nor possess infinite powers. Enlightenment, in the Buddhist sense, can grant some physic powers to practitioners. Of course, Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and many Chan Masters are perceived as enlightened figures. Given in Buddhist texts, they have some supernormal abilities, like clairvoyance and mind-reading. However, these abilities do not qualify enlightened individuals as "Supreme Gods."

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: It is not a theme of the text. No "previously human spirit," such as ancestor and human ghost, is present in the text.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Similar to the question above, spiritual beings, such as the Buddha, bodhisattvas, shapeshifters, and ghosts, exist. Often, in the Mahayana tradition, the Buddha and bodhisattvas are perceived as sacred beings. Since they are escaped from samsara (and deciding to stay in samsara in the forms of sentient beings), they are not technically "human," as one form of existences in samsara. Usually, as encounter dialogues, the gong'an cases record the speech and interactions between individuals (some of which are "supernormal/supernatural beings"). Thus, these beings can be sensed and cognized.

Reference: McRae, John R.. Seeing Through Zen. University of California Press, 2003.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Seeing_Through_Zen.html?hl=&id=vaYwDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Schlütter, Morten. How Zen Became Zen. University of Hawaii Press, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=_77cafb-ReQC.

Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as appeared in the text, these beings are visible.

Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Yes, people can talk to them.

Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: According to the idea of samsara, the world of sentient beings consists of six realms. Though many beings are not humans, they have sufficient knowledge about the world and can interact with beings in other realms/forms.

Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Solely reflected in Women Guan, the knowledge of spiritual beings, such as bodhisattvas, is not limited to one particular domain.

Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: The Buddhist cosmology is totally different from our modern sense of geography.

Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge is general about the Saha World.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge is general about the Saha World. It is based on Buddhist cosmology, but not the geographical area that uphold Buddhism.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

Notes: There is no mention of clairvoyance in the text.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

Notes: There is no mention of clairvoyance in the text.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: Although it is presumed as one of the skillful means of an advanced bodhisattva, however, the text does not offer any clue about it.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

Notes: It might be another skillful means. However, the text does not contain any related information.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: No mentions of prophecy in the text.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Clearly, many beings have advanced knowledge of Buddhism, as a means to reach nirvana. It is the knowledge of lokottara, which is not used for practical matters of this world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: First, the text includes zero indicating a casual efficacy created by supernatural beings.

Also, based on the classical Buddhist worldview, the Buddha and bodhisattvas cannot directly cause worldly benefits/punishments.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the recorded dialogues suggest that supernatural beings can communicate with other beings in the everyday life.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

Notes: No mention of dreams in the text.

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Notes: The text does not explicate any information about trance possession.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Divination is not discussed in the text.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Notes: It is hard to distinguish religious specialists from regular people. Also, regular people can teach Buddhism and communicate with others.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Notes: Monarch is not discussed in the text.

↳ Other?

– Specify: The spritual and supernatural beings are manifested in the human form to communicate with living beings.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: This sentence suits the Buddhist worldview best. These beings cannot directly bring salvation to the sentient beings but they preach the dharma which will eventually lead everyone to nirvana.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Solely based on the text, these supernatural beings do not exhibit any kind of emotion. They are characters that push the development of the plot.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: Solely based on the text, these supernatural beings do not exhibit any kind of emotion. They are characters that push the development of the plot.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: The text does not indicate any supernatural being possesses hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Supernatural beings in a Buddhist text mostly fit its worldview. The being could either be categorized into the five realms of existence (six realms except human) or is already enlightened. Of course, these beings, based on their statuses, possess their features respectively.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text scatteredly mentions the existence of supernatural beings. No ideas, akin to the pantheon, exist in the text. The text also does not contain any list of sacred beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Judging from a Buddhist perspective, an enlightened being (who has entered nirvana) can be considered as divine. Therefore, there is not a middle ground between the enlightened and the unenlightened, and such idea of "mixed human-divine beings" cannot survive under this perspective.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: The text does not require physical risk taking.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the supernatural beings that appeared in the text are described as physically present. They have physical bodies and interact with others (such as in the stories of Lady in Samadhi and Wild Fox Chan).

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: These beings have their bodies displayed, which means they are visible.

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, Chan/Zen literature sometimes even speaks against talking precepts. It is based upon the idea of non-duality. The following of ethical precepts is sometimes seen as a form of attachment to the conventional rules.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Although Buddhism and Buddhist text are predicated on the notion of six realms of rebirth, there is no explicit mention of this worldview in *Wumen Guan*. The text does not offer any category of beings.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: There is no marginalization mentioned in the text.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Scholastically speaking, Chan/Zen Buddhism (and Buddhism in general) is detached from divination practices. Solely based on the text, there is no mention of divination.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require any participation of rituals.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text does not require any participation of rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any related information.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The most common relationship in Buddhist monasticism is the master-disciple relationship. Because monastics practice celibacy, the master-disciple relationship sometimes is similar to father-son or mother-daughter relation. However, *Wumen Guan* does not employ such terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: From a modern, etic perspective, readers often find *Wumen Guan* entertaining. Many of its gong'an cases are fun and interesting. However, as a collection of the gong'an used during the meditation retreat, these stories are designed practical instead of entertaining.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text does not offer any related information.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The text is sometimes accompanied by calligraphy or a painting inspired by a gong'an case.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: Copy of *Wumen Guan* is often accompanied by the calligraphy of some of its key phrases or one central idea.

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: There are portrayals of the lineage masters and the paintings regarding the specific gong'an case.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are more than a dozen editions of *Wumen Guan*. Many editions have added prefaces or postscript, and some added a new case. One can also make commentaries on the cases and make them into new books. In general, the core contents remain the same. In modern days, the text is translated into multiple languages, and there are at least a dozen versions available in English. For more info, see <https://terebeess.hu/zen/mumonkan-eng.html>.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There is no core difference between different editions. The core content remains more or less the same.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Chan/Zen masters, after realizing their unique understanding of the gong'an cases, often add a new preface or postscript. The differentiation comes with these prefaces and postscript. They were added by different people and at different times. Some even add additional gong'an cases to the compilation.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Practitioners will follow the version that is convenient to them. Again, the contents of all the editions are almost the same. The preface and postscript do not really matter at the most of the time.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Wumen Guan is generally included in the post-Song Chinese Buddhist Canon as a Chan text.

Reference: Long, Darui, and Jinhua Chen. *Chinese Buddhist Canons in the Age of Printing*. Routledge, 2020. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_M3nDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Storch, Tanya. *The History of Chinese Buddhist Bibliography: Censorship and Transformation of the Tripitaka*. Cambria Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=e7J5CgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Lopez, Donald S.. *Buddhist Scriptures*. Penguin UK, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=6Pd-2IiIzip4C>.

Reference: Lock, Graham, and Gary S. Linebarger. *Chinese Buddhist Texts*. Routledge, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=btJMDwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: The text is commonly included in the post-Song Chinese Buddhist canon. As a Chan text, it cannot be found in the Pali and Tibetan canons.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The authority of the text is based on the authority of its author. Since Wumen Huikai was publically recognized as a renowned (and likely enlightened) Chan master, he has the authority and the influence to spread the text. As more people read the text and admit its value, the text was gradually canonized.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Buddhist canons are usually open canon. It means people can alter and add the canon according to the context.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: Since its initial inclusion into the canon, its canonicity was rarely questioned. Since then, Wumen Guan is a popular and authoritative Chan text.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: Wumen Guan is a stand-alone text. It means it was not composed as a part of a series nor designed for a larger textual corpse.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The text is very explicitly a scripture. Although it was not deemed as canonical as many of the sutras--since it was the instruction of a Chan master but not the Buddha--the text clearly has a religious orientation and is used for religious cultivation.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Menu

Notes: Wumen Guan is comprised of 48 gong'an cases. Before the main content, a menu, consisting of the titles of the 48 stories, is given. See http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T48n2005_001

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Although Chan Buddhism is famous for its construction of the notions of lineage master and lineage chart, Wumen Guan does not contain such a genealogy chart. The gong'an stories mention the names of many famous lineage masters, such as Zhaozhou Congnian and Baizhang Huaihan. However, the relationship between these masters is not explicated in the text. Also, the text does not name any Buddhist lineage.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Legal code is the subject matter of the Vinaya text. Chan gong'an collection is not related to the monastic rules.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: No religious calendar nor any dating is provided in the text.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not a topic in the text. On the contrary, Buddhism generally advocate the inseparability of spirit and the body (and deny the existence of a self).

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not give any systematic explanation of the afterlife. Though Buddhism typically stick to the idea of samsara (the six realms of rebirth), the text itself is not related to such discussion. At the same time, Chan/Zen Buddhism sometimes philosophically deny the existence of samsara.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The idea of reincarnation is employed in some cases of Wumen Guan. However, these stories are more rhetorical than doctrinal. The text does not specify any systematic idea of reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not give any related instruction.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text does not talk about burial nor sacrifices.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: No related idea is discussed in the text.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: No burial instruction or system is described in the text.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not presented in the text.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the definition of "supernatural beings." In some cases, spiritual beings, such as shapeshifters and ghosts, exist. For example, in case 2 (Wild Fox Chan), there is a shapeshifter fox (ex-Buddhist trapped in the fox shape; 於過去迦葉佛時。曾住此山。因學人間。大修行底人還落因果。也無。某甲對云。不落因果。五百生墮野狐身。今請和尚。). In some stories, enlightened Buddhist individuals, such as bodhisattvas, exist, such as the case of "Lady in Samadhi" (世尊昔因文殊至諸佛集處。值諸佛各還本處。)

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: The notion of a supreme high-god (as in the Judeo-Christian tradition) is lacking in Chan/Zen Buddhism. The answer to the question is determined by the definition of "Supreme High God." The Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and Chan lineage masters are not the creators of the universe nor possess infinite powers. Enlightenment, in the Buddhist sense, can grant some physic powers to practitioners. Of course, Buddha, Bodhisattvas, and many Chan Masters are perceived as enlightened figures. Given in Buddhist texts, they have some supernormal abilities, like clairvoyance and mind-reading. However, these abilities do not qualify enlightened individuals as "Supreme Gods."

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: It is not a theme of the text. No "previously human spirit," such as ancestor and human ghost, is present in the text.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Similar to the question above, spiritual beings, such as the Buddha, bodhisattvas, shapeshifters, and ghosts, exist. Often, in the Mahayana tradition, the Buddha and bodhisattvas are perceived as sacred beings. Since they are escaped from samsara (and deciding to stay in samsara in the forms of sentient beings), they are not technically "human," as one form of existences in samsara. Usually, as encounter dialogues, the gong'an cases record the speech and interactions between individuals (some of which are "supernormal/supernatural beings"). Thus, these beings can be sensed and cognized.

Reference: McRae, John R.. Seeing Through Zen. University of California Press, 2003.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Seeing_Through_Zen.html?hl=&id=vaYwDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Schlütter, Morten. How Zen Became Zen. University of Hawaii Press, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=_77cafb-ReQC.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as appeared in the text, these beings are visible.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Yes, people can talk to them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: According to the idea of samsara, the world of sentient beings consists of six realms. Though many beings are not humans, they have sufficient knowledge about the world and can interact with beings in other realms/forms.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No
Notes: Solely reflected in *Wumen Guan*, the knowledge of spiritual beings, such as bodhisattvas, is not limited to one particular domain.
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No
Notes: The Buddhist cosmology is totally different from our modern sense of geography.
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes
Notes: The knowledge is general about the Saha World.
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes
Notes: The knowledge is general about the Saha World. It is based on Buddhist cosmology, but not the geographical area that uphold Buddhism.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– No
Notes: There is no mention of clairvoyance in the text.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– No
Notes: There is no mention of clairvoyance in the text.
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– No
Notes: Although it is presumed as one of the skillful means of an advanced bodhisattva, however, the text does not offer any clue about it.
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– No
Notes: It might be another skillful means. However, the text does not contain any related information.
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– No

Notes: No mentions of prophecy in the text.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Clearly, many beings have advanced knowledge of Buddhism, as a means to reach nirvana. It is the knowledge of lokottara, which is not used for practical matters of this world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: First, the text includes zero indicating a casual efficacy created by supernatural beings. Also, based on the classical Buddhist worldview, the Buddha and bodhisattvas cannot directly cause worldly benefits/punishments.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the recorded dialogues suggest that supernatural beings can communicate with other beings in the everyday life.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

Notes: No mention of dreams in the text.

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Notes: The text does not explicate any information about trance possession.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Divination is not discussed in the text.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Notes: It is hard to distinguish religious specialists from regular people. Also, regular people can teach Buddhism and communicate with others.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Notes: Monarch is not discussed in the text.

↳ Other?

– Specify: The spritual and supernatural beings are manifested in the human form to communicate with living beings.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: This sentence suits the Buddhist worldview best. These beings cannot directly bring salvation to the sentient beings but they preach the dharma which will eventually lead everyone to nirvana.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Solely based on the text, these supernatural beings do not exhibit any kind of emotion. They are characters the push the development of the plot.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: Solely based on the text, these supernatural beings do not exhibit any kind of emotion. They are characters the push the development of the plot.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: The text does not indicate any supernatural being possesses hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Supernatural beings in a Buddhist text mostly fit its worldview. The being could either be categorized into the five realms of existence (six realms except human) or is already enlightened. Of course, these beings, based on their statuses, possess their features respectively.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text scatteredly mentions the existence of supernatural beings. No ideas, akin to the pantheon, exist in the text. The text also does not contain any list of sacred beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Judging from a Buddhist perspective, an enlightened being (who has entered nirvana) can be considered as divine. Therefore, there is not a middle ground between the enlightened and the unenlightened, and such idea of "mixed human-divine beings" cannot survive under this perspective.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the supernatural beings that appeared in the text are described as physically present. They have physical bodies and interact with others (such as in the stories of Lady in Samadhi and Wild Fox Chan).

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: These beings have their bodies displayed, which means they are visible.

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Although Buddhism and Buddhist text are predicated on the notion of six realms of rebirth, there is no explicit mention of this worldview in Wumen Guan. The text does not offer any category of beings.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Scholastically speaking, Chan/Zen Buddhism (and Buddhism in general) is detached from divination practices. Solely based on the text, there is no mention of divination.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not explicitly have any content relate to supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Some actions/results in the text can be seen as punishment. For example, in the case of Wild Fox Chan, the monastic was reborn into a fox because he failed to comprehend the nature of causation (hetu-phala). However, even we call it a punishment, such result is not meted out by any supernatural being.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Enlightened individuals can only teach certain things, but cannot straightforwardly bestow rewards. It depends on one's self to seek benefits from the teaching of the enlightened.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The Chan tradition is often characterized as a tradition of self-power, which means one can only rely on one's own effort to reach enlightenment. Though this image is constructed mainly by Japanese sectarians and projected back to Chinese Buddhist history, many Chan classics lack messianic figures. There is no belief that, the worship of a certain figure can lead the believers to salvation.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Albeit Buddhism generally has a few eschatologist theories, none of those appear in *Wumen Guan*. The Chan tradition is less associated with the idea of the beginning of a new epoch. It is also because Chan Buddhism lacks a messianic figure.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The text provides no social norms. They are the gong'an cases for religious practices.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The text does not make any moral requirement or distinction. No issue regarding morality or legality is discussed.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: Again, the text does not discuss any moral issues. And "virtue" is often not the best term used for the Buddhist tradition. One's salvation is gained from one's own practice and wisdom, but not the possession of virtues.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Upholding full sexual abstinence is presumed for Buddhist monastics. However, the text does not contain any code related to the subject.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify any rules about sexuality. It is presumed that all Buddhists need to obey the precepts, which include the constraint of sexual activities. However, *Wumen Guan* lack such content.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text contain no information about castration.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The text does not mention fasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Chinese/East Asian Buddhism has rigid precepts regarding the intake of food. However, *Wumen Guan* does not contain any information. Such topics are discussed in Vinaya text instead.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text mentions similar topics, such as the master cutting off the finger of the disciple in the story of One Finger Chan. However, it is not a requirement.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain related information.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The text does not discuss anything related to sacrifice.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: The text does not require physical risk taking.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, Chan/Zen literature sometimes even speaks against talking precepts. It is based upon the idea of non-duality. The following of ethical precepts is sometimes seen as a form of attachment to the conventional rules.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: There is no marginalization mentioned in the text.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require any participation of rituals.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text does not require any participation of rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not contain any related information.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The most common relationship in Buddhist monasticism is the master-disciple relationship. Because monastics practice celibacy, the master-disciple relationship sometimes is similar to father-son or mother-daughter relation. However, *Wumen Guan* does not employ such terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: From a modern, etic perspective, readers often find *Wumen Guan* entertaining. Many of its gong'an cases are fun and interesting. However, as a collection of the gong'an used during the meditation retreat, these stories are designed practical instead of entertaining.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text does not offer any related information.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: There is no mention of bureaucracy in the text.

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Although some cases involve violence (e.g., Nanquan's Cat), there is no mention of large-scale warfare or military activities.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A band

Notes: It is best to describe the medieval Chan tradition as a band. It was a voluntarily joined community with no clear sense of hierarchy. One gains its leading status by having proficient knowledge about Buddhism, very skillful meditation achievement, recognition from the lineage masters, and professional activities. Power, in this sense, is very personal. There is no rigid rules or social structure that determine one's leadership in the community.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify any form of taxation.

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: The text does not detail any interaction with public works.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Food production/disbursement is not a topic of the text.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in both pre-modern and modern times, gong'an cases are used in Buddhist monasteries. *Wumen Guan* was widely read and used in medieval China and Japan. Nowadays, it can be taught at meditation centers and universities throughout the world.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify any institutionalized famine relief.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify institutionalized poverty relief.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A band

Notes: The production of *Wumen Guan* was primarily used for meditation practice and the promotion of Buddhism. Thus, it was the monastics (the sangha) who produced the text. It is best to call the sangha a band because of its loose organization. In modern times, it has become a popular reader. The production of the text is facilitated by organizations that are dedicated to the promotion of Chan/Zen. Thus, it is also suitable to call them a band.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: Buddhist sangha, as a institution, is generally mentioned in the text. However, it was not specified as a body of education institution.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A state

Notes: In the post-Song imperial China, there were very few incidents of anti-Buddhist suppression. The biggest and most prominent anti-Buddhist event is the modern Communist suppression of religion. Thus, the destruction of the text is involved by the Chinese Communist government.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify institutionalized care for the elderly and the infirm.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not specify anything about non-religious education.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Wumen Guan talks briefly about the education of religious professionals. It deals with the general approach and method of practices toward liberation. It is likely the readership is intentionally monastic. However, solely based on the text, the text does not restrict education to religious professionals. Lay people can also study Wumen Guan and practice accordingly.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: The Chan/Zen gong'an collections typically is irrelevant from this-world politics and welfare.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text does not restrict education among religious professionals.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no mention of gender issue in the text.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: There is no mention of gender issue in the text.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text does not specify teaching relationships or ratios.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not advocate or specify any relationship to "teachers," because "teacher" is not a

proper term describing the relationship in Buddhism. Again, the relationship is best described as master-disciple. A Buddhist master, however, is not strictly a teacher or educator. The master is the disciple's teacher, head, and role-model. Regarding the Buddhist education in general, this master-disciple relationship is advocated frequently. *Wumen Guan* contains the notion and practice of lineage Chan masters, which is a type of master-disciple relationship.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: No worldly reward or benefit is associated to education in the text.

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

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Notes: It is best to describe the medieval Chan tradition as a band. It was a voluntarily joined community with no clear sense of hierarchy. One gains its leading status by having proficient knowledge about Buddhism, very skillful meditation achievement, recognition from the lineage masters, and professional activities. Power, in this sense, is very personal. There is no rigid rules or social structure that determine one's leadership in the community.

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Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not advocate or specify any relationship to "teachers," because "teacher" is not a proper term describing the relationship in Buddhism. Again, the relationship is best described as master-disciple. A Buddhist master, however, is not strictly a teacher or educator. The master is the disciple's teacher, head, and role-model. Regarding the Buddhist education in general, this master-disciple relationship is advocated frequently. *Women Guan* contains the notion and practice of lineage Chan masters, which is a type of master-disciple relationship.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: No worldly reward or benefit is associated to education in the text.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: There is no mention of bureaucracy in the text.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: The text does not detail any interaction with public works.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: The text does not specify any form of taxation.

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Although some cases involve violence (e.g., Nanquan's Cat), there is no mention of large-scale warfare or military activities.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Food production/disbursement is not a topic of the text.

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